

SMART METERING WITH DSM TECHNIQUE TO REDUCE DEMAND ENERGY FOR COMMERCIAL CONSUMERS IN SOUTH AFRICA

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Abstract:

Energy efficiency in the world has been on the rising trend due to increasing energy costs and the environmental problem caused by greenhouse emissions. South Africa has committed and introduced the demand side management strategy to encourage energy efficiency and use of technology to local consumers. The paper aimed to propose possible demand side management technique to improve industrial's electrical system efficiency. The methodology followed in the paper is the employment of the facility smart metering together with capacitor banks to absorb the reactive energy demand required by facility equipment and system to operate. Further explored the integration of smart metering to easily monitor and store power data for proper power factor correction of facility. The findings are such that poor power factor affect efficiency of electrical system, as a results increases the electricity cost. However, overcorrected electrical system causes harmonic distortion, which is harmful to electrical systems. For that reason a balanced approach is applied on this paper. The report is compiled to reveal the design solution for the reduction of electricity bill and promote efficient use of facility electricity.

Keywords: Energy, efficiency, power factor, smart metering

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I. INTRODUCTION

Energy in the world is the most important commodity that each country needs to grow the economy, create employment, and reduce the lack of access that exists. In the late 1970s, the energy producers of the United States introduced and implemented the program purposed at changing the level and timing of energy demand among customers which is called demand-side management (DSM)[18]. The DSM aimed to encourage efficient use of energy together with technology to relieve the pressure imposed on the national grid. In 2005, the South African government introduced the national energy efficiency strategy (NEES) aimed to respond to the increasing demand for energy alongside a growing commitment to improving resource utilization and cutting down on environmental polluters [19]. The commercial sector under NEES set a reduction target of 15% by 2015. The City of Cape Town committed to lead by example and improve the energy efficiency that consumed by city buildings. The research paper aimed to demonstrate implementation of smart metering with power factor correction (PFC) to reduce demand power of facility. The End-product should be beneficial to SASOL in terms of reduction of total electricity bill.

The report paper is arranged as follows: section I introduction and discussions on related literature reviews, section II discusses research site and proposed design setup, section III illustrates theoretical and practical experimental, section IV describes and discusses the results and lastly section V describes conclusion and findings.

A. RELATED LITERATURE REVIEW

Access to electricity is accepted as the demonstrator of socio-economic development of any country [6], [8]. In 2012, the International Energy Agency (IEA) [9] reported that Sub-Saharan Africa has 589 million people and that 56.9% of the population did not have access to electricity, while only 43.1% have electrification. The same study, in 2012 indicated that the population in Africa is predicted to grow by 71% from 2009 to 2035, but there will be only a 38% increase in energy demand over the same period [9]. This means that as the African population increases from 2009 (by 15%) to the estimated 2035 (by 20%), then the global energy share will decline fractionally to 5.4% over the same predicted period [10]. This leads to considerable benefits of investing in efficient energy use and energy efficiency technologies. The utilization of efficiency systems increases the supply energy bandwidth to the consumers. This efficiency system involves the utilization of the smart grid and demand side management.

The supply and demand load should be constantly balanced to avoid interference in supply systems or causing extremely high demand [24]. The demand side management programs have been praised and gained popularity as an intelligent program to optimize features of electricity consumption reference to the overall consumption picture, time profile, and other parameters in order to achieve savings in electricity charges [12]. These reasons influence consumers' decision to utilize DSM for the benefit of reducing the electricity bill and peak demand [13]. The Nghiem study [11] argued that most industry energy structures find themselves exposed to a demand price 200 times higher than the nominal power rate, which could be extremely expensive and lead to inefficient energy consumption. The other study stated that in Hong Kong, the commercial buildings consume 60% of total electricity and 50% comes from Air Conditioning (AC) systems [14]. Building structures can play a vital role in load balancing regulation and grid operation systems such as the thermal load storage and considering demand load control e.g. load shifting, peak shaving and peak demand limit/set-point [14]. It was revealed that load shifting and load shedding are not the correct approaches to balance power consumption, as it does not aid in decoupling energy sinks [13]. However, these DSM techniques can efficiently operate with smart technologies and grids.

Power factor correction (PFC) could be used as DSM technique to improve facility electrical efficiency of commercial and industrial businesses. PFC is defined as a process of compensating a lagging current by a leading current with the use of capacitance [16]. Theoretically, the adjusted power factor should be equivalent to unity, meaning the capacitors must produce 100% reactive power that is needed. However, in practise correcting power factor closer to unity has disadvantage such as possibility of causing harmonic distortion, which would add more problems to the system[21],[16]. The PFC function is to neutralise amount of the reactive current as possible to reduce loss in the distribution system. Modern PFC has smart controller that automatically control and manage capacitance. The smart metering has gained momentum in the world for easy management and control of electricity demand consumption [2]. The smart devices provide many opportunities in the smart grid environment by providing a flexible

exchange of information from devices and controllers for efficient control, management and optimisation [3]. The core function of the smart metering is to use digital communication and control systems to monitor and control power flows with the purpose of converting the power grid to be resilient, efficient, and cost effective [2]. This Smart technology allows facility produced energy to be plugged into the internal electricity board to supplement the power supply from utility and other suppliers. The Infrastructural design of smart grid is based on the specific objectives and capabilities [1]. The interconnection via Modbus protocols is to permit exchange of information and storage [20], [4]. The combination of PFC and smart metering offers number of benefits to the commercial customers, including reduced electricity bill by removing charges of reactive power and gaining extra apparent power existing from installed system.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Site: SASOL

SASOL fuels application centre (SFAC) is a state-of art SASOL facility in Cape Town, Muizenberg. The facility's core-function is fuels research and development. The fuels tests performed are based on national and international standards. This fuels test application uses vehicle engines and various monitoring equipment as tools to archive their intended purpose. As a results high amount of electricity is needed to drive all machineries and monitoring equipment, which results in high cost of electricity. According to facility electricity bill, the demand power cost is twice the real power, which result in high total electricity cost. The SFAC facility needs to perform the following.

- Improve operation efficiency of electricity in the facility
- Reduce the cost of electricity

B. Proposed design system

The proposed system input of 420Vac at 50Hz main supply to supply power factor correction bank and 230Vac at 50Hz to supply smart metering power supply and equipment as shown in Figure 1&2. The power supply unit in Figure 2, then convert 230Vac to 24Vdc, which powers all power meters, gateways, communication modules and other equipment.

new capacity that makes it simpler to protect assets, keep operations running and save time and money.

However, the grouping of PFC and smart metering could offer number of benefits to SFAC, which includes elimination of charges on reactive power. As a results facility gains extra apparent power existing from installed system.

III. EXPERIMENTATION

The research experiments are divided into two parts theoretical and practical experiments.

A. Theoretical experiments

The theoretical approach begins with power triangle relationships to determine the required reactive power. The theoretical knowledge is based on power triangle relationship with power factor, shown in Figure 3. The design simulator created in figure 5 below helped to simulate the power parameters of facility in order to help with practical design system. The simulator made up of 1MVA/420V transformer, which feed the main board and facility load. The power factor defined as a ratio between real power and apparent power.

Fig. 3. Power triangle relationships [22].

The facility highest measured real power were applied and two assumptions cases were made for power factor to be between 85% and 99%, to better understand power parameters behaviour. Now, to obtain the unity power factor, the rule of the thumb as:

$$PF = P/S = \cos(\Theta) \quad (1)$$

Where PF is a power factor measured in fraction, S is apparent power measure in VA and P as real power measured in watts [16].

$$Q^2 + P^2 = S^2 \quad (2)$$

Where the Q presents the reactive power measured in Volt-Ampere Reactive (VAR). The required Q calculated as difference between corrected and uncorrected VAR.

$$\text{Required } Q = Q_{\text{uncorrected}} - Q_{\text{corrected}} \quad (3)$$

$$C = \text{VAR} / 2\pi f V^2 \quad (4)$$

Where C is a capacitance measured in farad, f is frequency measured in hertz, and V as voltage measured in volts [22]. The simulator software in Figure 5 is a Microsoft excel design simulator that can give many important power information. These information include before and after power factor correction and different local.

B. Practical Experiments

The practical approach of the system is based on power parameters that are automatically measured, processed by smart meters and transfer power information to controllers. As shown in the flowchart, the system acceptable PF=0.99, otherwise the controller activates the PFC required steps for reactive power compensation. The following Figure 4 illustrates the functional flowchart of the system.

Fig. 4. Practical design flowchart

C. Findings: Experiments

Both practical and theoretical experiments have shown improvements on the facility power factor as capacitors are applied to the system. However, a careful design consideration of the type of load the system will be supplying is critical and then design accordingly to avoid overcorrecting which could cause harmonic distortions in the system. The power factor of unity, meaning to push up power factor to 100% have shown a possibility of over correcting the system. However, capacitor with smaller (in farad) value are good to fine tune the system for accurate correction. The smart metering gives management power to monitor, analyse and investigate any electrical problems on their system. It also gives opportunity for internet of things.

Fig. 5. Design simulator for PFC

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To demonstrate the working of smart metering together with PFC for SFAC facility, the power parameters are shown on power metering expert (PME) software in Figure 6 below. The system is connected to 420Vac Board and different facility loads are automatic applied as facility operations take place. The inductive loads cause high reactive power need, however PFC controller can determine the required reactive power demand for lifting up power factor up to 0.99. This process is done intelligently by PFC controller which switches on capacitors from the capacitor bank based on required reactive power demand.

Fig. 6. Practical design simulation with PFC

The Figure shown a corrected power factor at 0.984, while it keeps measured the real power and apparent power are at the same value. The reactive power of main supply become zero, and PFC discharges 22,6kVAR to correct the facility power factor. And the PFC controller as shown in Figures 7 below activated the steps to compensate

for required reactive power. The effectiveness of power factor correction's capacitors is clear shown by the percentage value of displacement PF, the higher percentage indicates good quality capacitors. As is shown Figure 8 below as displacement PF -100%.

Step	Step Status		Step Capacity			Switching Cycles	Step Alarm
	Operational	Status	Initial	Present	Remaining		
	Step 01	✓	⚡	-100 998 VAR	-100 857 VAR		
Step 02	✓	⚡	-101 204 VAR	-101 310 VAR	100 %	187	Inactive
Step 03	✓	⚡	0 VAR	-243 207 VAR	%	18	
Step 04	✓	⚡	0 VAR	-248 075 VAR	%	18	
Step 05	✓	⚡	0 VAR	-250 591 VAR	%	18	
Step 06	✓	⚡	0 VAR	-245 806 VAR	%	18	

Fig. 7. PFC with activated steps

Fig. 8. PFC with display of PF and displacement PF

V. CONCLUSIONS

The smart metering and power factor correct applied in SFAC facility can be used in commercial and industrial sector to increase stability and efficiency of the electrical system. However, high level of responsible maintenance and inspections to capacitors should be done to avoid occurrence of harmonics distortion, switching arc which could lower the lifespan of capacitor bank [23], [22]. The smart metering with PFC system helps the facility electrical system to substitute grid drawn current with PFC current and reduce charges on electricity charges. It is evident that reduced facility electrical consumption relieves strains to Utility supply with demand and assist in reduction of greenhouse gases.

Findings: Although this system improves power factor efficiency, SFAC management should consider investigating the best tariff structure that fit for their operation. Because currently facility is on flat rate tariff structure which could be more expensive compare to time of use.

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